

LINGUOPROSE AS A METHOD FOR THE ANALYSIS OF LITERARY TEXT

Dauletmuratova Xurziya Elubaevna

Senior teacher, Nukus State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20196363>

Abstract. *This article examines linguoprose as a method for the analysis of literary text and explores its theoretical and methodological foundations as an independent scientific direction in modern linguistics. Unlike traditional linguostylistics, which studies various types of texts, linguoprose focuses exclusively on the linguistic features of literary prose. The study analyzes the specific characteristics of prosaic literary language (narrativeness, time dynamics, cause-and-effect relationships, multi-layered speech, and hidden rhythm), its dialogical nature (M.M. Bakhtin), and its social orientation. Particular attention is paid to the differences between prosaic and poetic language, the syntactic and stylistic devices typical of prose (aposiopesis, parcellation, ellipsis, etc.), and the limitations of traditional literary analysis. The author substantiates the necessity of linguoprose as a systematic method for the comprehensive study of the language of literary texts as a unique linguistic phenomenon and proposes a functional-comparative approach to their analysis.*

Keywords: *linguoprose, literary text, artistic prose, linguostylistic analysis, dialogism, hidden rhythm, syntactic devices, functional-comparative analysis*

Аннотация. *В статье лингвопроза рассматривается как метод анализа литературного текста, исследуются его теоретические и методологические основы как самостоятельного научного направления в современной лингвистике. В отличие от традиционной лингвостилистики, изучающей различные типы текстов, лингвопроза сосредоточена исключительно на языковых особенностях художественной прозы. Исследование анализирует специфические характеристики прозаического художественного языка (повествовательность, временная динамика, причинно-следственные связи, многослойность речи и скрытый ритм), его диалогическую природу (М.М. Бахтин) и социальную направленность. Особое внимание уделяется различиям между прозаическим и поэтическим языком, синтаксическим и стилистическим средствам, характерным для прозы (апосиопеза, парцелляция, эллипсис и др.), а также ограничениям традиционного литературоведческого анализа. Автор обосновывает необходимость лингвопрозы как системного метода комплексного изучения языка литературных текстов как уникального лингвистического феномена и предлагает функционально-сопоставительный подход к их анализу.*

Ключевые слова: *лингвопроза, литературный текст, художественная проза, лингвостилистический анализ, диалогизм, скрытый ритм, синтаксические средства, функционально-сопоставительный анализ*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada lingvoproza adabiy matnni tahlil qilish metodi sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi va zamonaviy tilshunoslikdagi mustaqil ilmiy yo'nalish sifatida uning nazariy va metodologik asoslari o'rganiladi. An'anaviy lingvostilistika turli matn turlarini o'rganishdan farqli o'laroq, lingvoproza faqat badiiy proza tilining o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga qaratilgan. Tadqiqot prozaik badiiy tilning o'ziga xos belgilari (hikoyachilik, vaqt dinamikasi, sabab-natija*

bog‘lanishlari, nutqning ko‘p qatlamligi, yashirin ritm), uning dialogik tabiati (M.M. Baxtin) va ijtimoiy yo‘nalishini tahlil qiladi. Proza va she‘riy til o‘rtasidagi farqlar, prozaga xos sintaktik va stilistik vositalar (aposiopesis, parsellatsiya, ellips va boshqalar) hamda an‘anaviy adabiy tahlilning cheklovlari alohida e‘tibor qaratiladi. Muallif lingvoprozani adabiy matnlar tilini noyob lingvistik hodisa sifatida tizimli va kompleks o‘rganishning zaruriy metodi sifatida asoslab, ularni funksional-qiyosiy tahlil qilish yondashuvini taklif etadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *lingvoproza, adabiy matn, badiiy proza, lingvostilistik tahlil, dialogizm, yashirin ritm, sintaktik vositalar, funksional-qiyosiy tahlil*

Prose – compared to poetry – is a type of literary verbal art that is not organized on the basis of rhythm, but is primarily based on narration, description, and analysis. In prose, reality is depicted broadly, oriented toward cause-and-effect relationships, psychological motivation, and social context. In the words of Ernest Hemingway, “Prose is not interior decoration, but architecture”¹.

The main characteristics of prose are as follows:

- narrativeness – the presence of a narrator, the sequence of events, and the existence of fabula and plot;
- time interval – the development of action over time;
- cause-and-effect relationships – the logic of events and the actions of characters;
- typification of images – the reflection of social and historical characters;
- multi-layered speech – the interaction between the author’s word, the characters’ words, and internal monologue.

From the linguostylistic point of view, artistic prose is a complex word (speech) structure that performs not only a communicative function but also an aesthetic one.

According to the British writer, journalist, and critic George Orwell: “Good prose should be as clear as a mirror” – meaning that the reader should understand not the language itself, but the idea². We interpret this opinion as following: the language of literary work should be understandable, precise, and natural, so that the reader perceives not the form of narration, but primarily the idea, image, and content. The true skill of the writer lies in creating a text in which the word does not obstruct the idea but serves it.

The famous American prose writer John Cheever said about prose: “The surface of good prose is where you can hear the sound of rain and the sound of battle”.³ This opinion shows that a true prose text is capable of conveying at the same time both the calm, hidden (intimate) anxieties of human life and large-scale dramatic events. On a single page of such a text, various levels of human experience – from quiet, barely perceptible feelings to powerful dramatic clashes – can coexist. It is precisely this ability to combine different aspects of life that makes prose rich, lively, and artistic.

¹ <https://www.brainyquote.com/topics/prose-quotes?> (múrátat etilgen sáne: 25.02.2026)

² Life & Wisdom Quote by George Orwell <https://fixquotes.com/quotes/good-writing-is-like-a-windowpane-28279/> (múrátat etilgen sáne: 08.03.2026)

³ Inspiring Quotes About Reading (by Famous Authors). By Jess Esa and Willow Heath / 12th September 2023 <https://booksandbao.com/inspiring-quotes-about-reading-by-famous-authors> (múrátat etilgen sáne: 25.02.2026).

The 1987 Nobel Prize laureate in literature Joseph Brodsky stated: “Prose, at its root, enters into social relations”⁴ – expressing the idea that prose as a genre is closely connected with word and social experience. The connection of prose with social relations defines its realistic orientation. Prose strives to depict life in all its contradictions and difficulties exactly as it is in reality. Therefore, the language and form of prose are aimed at being understandable, natural, and credible so that the reader perceives the depicted world as part of real social reality.

The prominent Russian linguist V.V. Vinogradov, in his book *On the Language of Artistic Prose*, addresses the tasks of stylistics, the language of artistic and literary works, the history of the relationship between the Russian language and Russian literature, compositional speech categories of literature, the social system of language and individual linguistic creativity, poetics and rhetoric, and other issues. In this work, V.V. Vinogradov considers artistic prose as “an artistic system of word (speech) forms”⁵. Lexis, syntax, intonation, and stylistic devices work together to create the imagery and literary content of the text. According to the scholar, the writer’s style emerges through word choice, sentence structure, types of narration, and the composition of the text.

In prose theory, the “dialogical” concept developed by M.M. Bakhtin also occupies a special place. In his view, “Prose is dialogical by its very nature”⁶ – that is, in prose various concepts, viewpoints, and speech styles interact with each other. The scholar also viewed prose as a field for the interaction of different voices, viewpoints, and consciousnesses. This feature is particularly evident in the way the writer organizes dialogue between characters, ideas, and positions without imposing a single truth.

Linguists Q. Jarimbetov and B. Genjemuratov distinguish between two types of literary language: poetic language and prosaic language. The authors pay special attention to both and attempt to identify the main similarities and differences inherent in them. “Prosaic artistic language is distinguished by paragraphs, its own sentences, chains of sentences, lines, and simple oral sentences. There is also rhythm in prose, but it is not as immediately noticeable as in poetry. Studying this phenomenon is more difficult... Prosaic language is simple and natural, possessing clarity and concreteness”⁷. In prose, rhythm does not obey a strict metric system; nevertheless, it is created through other means:

- sentence length;
- pauses and intonation;
- repetition of words or constructions;
- syntactic parallelism;
- alternation of short and long phrases.

Therefore, rhythm in prose is free and hidden.

In poetry, strict meter, equally structured lines, rhyme, and rhythm are immediately audible, whereas in prose, the rhythm is free, sentences vary in length, there is no rhyme, and perceiving the rhythm is more important than hearing it. Consequently, rhythm in prose does not “shine” or stand out as it does in poetry.

⁴ <https://www.brainyquote.com/topics/prose-quotes> (múrâjat etilgen sáne: 25.02.2026)

⁵ Виноградов В.В. О языке художественной прозы. – М.: Наука, 1980. – С. 5–12.

⁶ Бахтин М.М. Проблемы поэтики Достоевского. – М.: Советский писатель, 1963. – С. 71–78.

⁷ Jarimbetov Q., Genjemuratov B. Adebifat teoriyası. – Tashkent, «Sano-standart» baspası, 2018. – B. 139.

Thus, prose is a complex system of language and ideas; it does not merely narrate objective reality but interprets it – explains and clarifies it. It is a form of verbal art that reveals the consciousness and psychology of humanity, society, and a particular era. Every level in it (word, sentence, text) works to create ideas and thoughts. Although existing trends in modern linguistics are sufficient for studying prose works, we consider a linguoprosaic approach necessary to examine prose as a unique phenomenon in its own right. Prosaic works occupy a special place in the literature of every nation. Their distinctive features require a separate type of analysis – linguoprosaic analysis.

In the study of prosaic works, it is recommended to primarily use linguostylistic, lexical-semantic, discourse, cognitive, pragmatic, text-linguistic, and narratological types of analysis. Linguoprose does not restrict the use of these types of analysis. They are of particular importance in defining the methodological base and research principles of linguoprose.

It is gradually becoming evident that linguostylistic analysis alone is insufficient for the complex study of artistic prosaic text. In linguostylistics, any creation (scientific texts, lyrical poems, journalistic texts, etc.) can be the object of research. In linguoprose, however, only prosaic works are studied. In this respect, linguostylistics covers a broader scope. Nevertheless, just as “linguostylistic analysis serves as the basis for linguopoetic analysis”⁸ linguoprosaic analysis also uses it as its foundation. First, linguostylistic analysis is applied to determine the artistic level of the language units in the work. Then their functions in image creation are examined, along with the psychology of the characters and the peculiarities of revealing their word portraits, their participation in the dynamics of word change in the work, their influence on the narrative form, the realization of the author’s thinking potential in the prosaic work, and a number of other issues.

When analyzing the language of prosaic works from a linguistic perspective, the following shortcomings must be avoided:

- retelling the content of the work;
- describing the characters from a literary-studies point of view;
- limiting the analysis to “the author will say it this way”;
- drifting into philosophical ideas;
- analyzing everything together – language, image, plot, and idea;
- studying all internal language systems (phonetics, lexicology, morphology, syntax).

Linguoprosaic analysis involves selecting a limited number of language units and subjecting them to comprehensive analysis. Linguoprose treats the prosaic text not as a literary genre, but as an object of linguistics – a free language system.

The specificity of the prosaic text is primarily related to its word (speech) dynamics. In prose, the character’s thought is never fully and sequentially narrated; instead, it stops, is interrupted, begins again, and is enriched by internal speech. Syntactic phenomena such as aposiopesis, parcellation, ellipsis, rhetorical question, and artistic repetition – along with other literary devices – are characteristic of prosaic language. They convey the character’s inner experiences, spiritual contradictions, and subjective evaluations. The systematic analysis of these speech mechanisms serves to reveal the essence of the linguoprosaic approach.

In contemporary linguistics, linguoprose develops in continuous connection with such fields as text linguistics, pragmalinguistics, functional stylistics, and cognitive linguistics. In this

⁸ Липгарт А.А. Основы линвопоэтики. – М.: Книжный дом «ЛИБРОКОМ», 2021. – С. 110.

direction, the prosaic text is viewed not merely as a collection of language units, but as a complex system that reflects communicative purpose, speech subjectivity, and interaction with the reader. Especially in the comparative analysis of prosaic works in different languages, the linguoprosaic approach yields high scientific results. This is because it makes it possible to reveal national or cultural differences not through subjective evaluations, but on the basis of precise linguistic norms.

Summing up, linguoprose is forming as an independent scientific direction aimed at the in-depth and systematic study of the linguistic features of prose, without confining it within the framework of literary studies. This approach creates a solid theoretical and methodological foundation for the functional and comparative analysis of the language tools used, for example, in creating the image of a woman in prosaic text.

References

1. Бахтин М.М. Проблемы поэтики Достоевского. – М.: Советский писатель, 1963. – С. 71–78
2. Виноградов В.В. О языке художественной прозы. – М.: Наука, 1980. – С. 5–12.
3. Липгарт А.А. Основы линвопоэтики. – М.: Книжный дом «ЛИБРОКОМ», 2021. – С. 110.
4. Jarimbetov Q., Genjemuratov B. Adebiyat teoriyası. – Tashkent, «Sano-standart» baspası, 2018. – B. 139.
5. <https://www.brainyquote.com/topics/prose-quotes?> (múrąjat etilgen sáne: 25.02.2026)
6. Life & Wisdom Quote by George Orwell <https://fixquotes.com/quotes/good-writing-is-like-a-windowpane-28279/> (múrąjat etilgen sáne: 08.03.2026)
7. Inspiring Quotes About Reading (by Famous Authors). By Jess Esa and Willow Heath / 12th September 2023 <https://booksandbao.com/inspiring-quotes-about-reading-by-famous-authors> (múrąjat etilgen sáne: 25.02.2026).
8. <https://www.brainyquote.com/topics/prose-quotes> (múrąjat etilgen sáne: 25.02.2026)